
A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF A DOMAIN-SPECIFIC SLM AND A GENERAL-PURPOSE LLM FOR TITLE GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

The increasing adoption of artificial intelligence in journalism has created demand for language models that can support editorial workflows while complying with legal, ethical, and organizational requirements. In particular, concerns regarding copyrighted training data, transparency, and operational control have motivated interest in domain-specific small language models (SLMs) that can be trained entirely on licensed content. This study investigates the extent to which a custom domain-specific SLM is suitable for title generation in a journalistic environment when compared with the general-purpose large language model GPT-4o. The project was realized in cooperation with the Austria Presse Agentur (APA). Its primary objective is to provide a local alternative to external LLMs such as GPT-4o. The model was trained exclusively on data from the APA news archive to ensure that only licensed material was used. The development process involved selecting a tokenizer, model architecture, and training parameters. Both automated and human evaluations were conducted to assess differences between title suggestions generated by the SLM, GPT-4o, and the original titles of the source texts. The BERTScore and ROUGE-L indicate that the titles generated by the SLM are closer to the original reference titles. However, the examples generated by the LLM are preferred by human evaluators. Further improvements are needed in the training data, the model configuration and the training approach.

Keywords Small Language Models, Large Language Models, Title Generation, Journalism, GPT-4o, BERTScore, ROUGE-L

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence has become increasingly integrated into journalistic production and editorial workflows [1]. Large language models (LLMs) have enabled applications such as summarization, proofreading, and headline creation [2]. These models offer significant productivity gains but also raise concerns regarding transparency [3], copyright compliance and the usage of unlicensed training data [4] as well as potential model biases [3]. At the same time, emerging regulatory frameworks increasingly emphasize transparency regarding training data sources and model development practices [5].

An alternative approach involves the development of domain-specific small language models (SLMs). Such models require less memory during training and deployment than LLMs and can reduce costs [6]. Furthermore, they can be developed in environments with limited computational resources. The smaller architecture is also less energy intensive [6] and more sustainable than large-scale models [6]. They can offer a reduced latency compared to LLMs while maintaining a sufficient performance as long as the use case remains specific [6]. There have even been cases where SLMs with a smaller architecture and less available training data have shown a better performance than LLMs [7]. A model with 500M parameters, for example, has been able to outperform GPT-4o on two benchmarks for mathematical problems [8]. Thus, the larger size of an LLM does not necessarily mean better results. Another major benefit of SLMs

is their adaptability since they can be fine-tuned to serve a specific task in a relatively short time [6]. Generally speaking, larger models require more training data than smaller models to reach their optimal performance [9]. Depending on the task, an SLM should be able to generate sufficient results with less training data. This is particularly useful when the amount of available data is limited.

In general, SLMs that have been trained on clean data could utilize these benefits and address the issues regarding larger models. Thus, this study was conducted in cooperation with the APA-IT Informations Technologie GmbH, alias APA-Tech, in order to investigate whether a domain-specific SLM trained solely on licensed journalistic content can provide a viable alternative to a general-purpose LLM like GPT-4o for title generation. Thus, the research question addressed in this work is:

To what extent is a custom domain-specific SLM suitable for title generation in a journalistic context compared to the general-purpose LLM GPT-4o?

2 Methods

Two common strategies for developing a task-specific model are fine-tuning a pre-existing pretrained model or training a smaller "student" model via knowledge distillation (KD) from a larger "teacher" model [10]. Both approaches were rejected because they introduce dependence on a model that may itself have been trained on unlicensed data and in the case of KD, could carry over some of the privacy and memorization risks associated with the teacher model [11, 12]. Instead, a two-stage training strategy was adopted which consisted of pretraining followed by task-specific fine-tuning. Unlike approaches that adapt an existing model, the model was trained from scratch to avoid dependence on potentially unlicensed training data. The objective of the pretraining phase was to create a general German-language completion model capable of generating coherent journalistic text. Fine-tuning subsequently specialized the model for title generation based on article content.

2.1 Training Data

The training data were obtained exclusively from the APA news archive. The use of this data ensured compliance with the legal requirements while providing a domain-specific corpus. The dataset consists of 6,349,227 samples and has a total size of $\sim 8.96GB$. This dataset has been used for pretraining and fine-tuning the SLM. The publication dates of the articles in the first dataset range from the beginning of 1985 until the end of June 2025. Each sample in the set is composed of the title and content of a corresponding APA news item.

2.2 Tokenizer

A custom Byte-Pair Encoding (BPE) tokenizer was trained using the Hugging Face Tokenizers library [13]. BPE was selected over alternative subword tokenization schemes including WordPiece, Unigram and Word-level on the basis of its transparency, determinism, and widespread adoption in contemporary LLMs [14]. A vocabulary size of 52,000 tokens was selected, based on common ranges reported for monolingual models [15], with a minimum pair frequency of two. Unicode normalization (NFC) and a ByteLevel pre-tokenizer without an added leading space were used so that whitespace is explicitly represented within tokens. Nineteen special tokens were added, including padding and end-of-sequence tokens as well as reserved tokens for potential future prompting schemes, including dedicated delimiter tokens for content and title used during fine-tuning. The resulting tokenizer has a size of approximately 3.70 MB.

2.3 Model architecture

A decoder-only transformer architecture was selected, based on evidence that decoder-only models are generally well suited to open-ended text generation and perform competitively under zero-shot conditions [16, 17]. Specifically, the model was implemented using the Gemma3CausalLM configuration [18], motivated by its design emphasis on efficient fine-tuning and deployment on resource-constrained hardware [19, 20].

The default Gemma3 configuration corresponds to approximately $2.63B$ parameters and was substantially reduced for this prototype. The vocabulary size (52,000) was set to match the custom tokenizer. The hidden size (640) follows a value previously used as a baseline in a knowledge-distillation study [18]; the intermediate size (2,500) was set to approximately four times the hidden size, consistent with common practice [21]. The number of attention heads and key-value heads were both set to eight for Multi-Head Attention [22] and the number of hidden layers was reduced from the Gemma3 default of 24 to eight, in order to limit the overall parameter count. A maximum sequence length of 1,024 tokens was chosen as a moderate value relative to common ranges for transformer language models [23, 24]. All

remaining parameters were left at their Gemma3TextConfig default values. The resulting model has approximately 113.6M parameters and a file size of approximately 433 MB (excluding tokenizer files).

2.4 Reference titles from GPT-4o

To obtain comparison titles from a general-purpose LLM, GPT-4o was queried for each article in the evaluation set using a fixed system prompt. A minimal custom prompt was used, informed by prior work on prompting for concise title generation [25, 26]:

"Verfasse einen kurzen Titel für diesen Text:" (English: "Write a short title for this text:")

2.5 Automated evaluation

Two automated metrics were used to assess the similarity between generated titles and the original, human-written titles for the 1,000 articles in the evaluation set. The F1 variant of ROUGE-L, which measures lexical overlap based on the longest common subsequence [27] and the BERTScore, which measures semantic similarity via cosine similarity of contextual embeddings from a pretrained BERT-family model [28, 29]. Both metrics have previously been used for the evaluation of text summarization and title generation [30, 25].

Since the BERTScore can depend on the choice of the underlying embedding model, five pretrained models were used in combination: `bert-base-german-cased`, `bert-base-german-uncased`, `gbert-base` (German BERT base), `GottBERT`, and a multilingual model, `multilingual-e5-base` [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36]. Both ROUGE-L and BERTScore were computed for all three pairwise comparisons among (i) SLM-generated titles, (ii) GPT-4o-generated titles, and (iii) the original titles. For the SLM, sampling was disabled to make the results reproducible.

2.6 Human evaluation

Automated metrics such as ROUGE-L and BERTScore do not always correspond well to human judgments of text quality [37, 38] and human preference judgments are commonly used to compare LLM-generated text [39, 40]. A ranking-based human evaluation was therefore conducted with five participants recruited from media departments at APA. For each of 100 randomly selected articles from the evaluation set, participants were shown the article text together with three candidate titles consisting of the original title, the SLM-generated title and the GPT-4o-generated title. The titles were presented in a randomized order without any indication of origin. Each participant ranked all three titles for each of the 100 articles according to their preference.

To test for systematic differences in rank distributions among the three title types, a Friedman test was applied [41], with the following hypotheses:

- H_0 : The distributions of ranks are identical across the three title types. There is no statistically significant preference between original titles and titles generated by GPT-4o or the custom SLM.
- H_1 : At least one title type differs in its rank distribution from the others. There is a statistically significant preference for at least one of the three title origins.

To identify which pairwise comparisons were statistically significant, three Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted for the pairs: original vs. SLM, original vs. GPT-4o and SLM vs. GPT-4o [42].

2.7 Inference time measurement

The inference time of the final fine-tuned SLM and of GPT-4o was measured during generation of titles for all 1,000 evaluation samples. The SLM was run locally on the development server without additional overhead, whereas the inference time of GPT-4o was obtained as request-duration metadata returned by the production APA-Text-Assistant application under normal deployment conditions. The comparison is therefore indicative rather than strictly controlled, as GPT-4o latency includes network and external API processing overhead, while the SLM measurement reflects local execution only.

3 Results

3.1 Pretraining

An initial pretraining run was conducted on a 10% subset of the training corpus using default learning-rate settings (initial learning rate 5×10^{-5} , linear decay, no warm-up, batch size 32). Training loss decreased rapidly during the first epoch and continued to decrease, more slowly, over subsequent epochs, beginning to plateau toward the start of the fourth epoch; small but consistent drops in loss were observed at each epoch transition, a pattern previously associated with optimizer behavior upon re-exposure to previously seen samples [43]. Qualitative inspection of generated completions showed that the model could produce German text thematically related to the prompt (e.g. correctly associating political entities such as "Österreich", "ÖVP", "SPÖ", and "EU"), but output was frequently ungrammatical and lacked coherent overall structure or factual accuracy.

Further hyperparameter tuning runs using higher initial learning rates (2×10^{-4} and 4×10^{-4} , with a 3% warm-up ratio) reduced the overall training loss relative to the initial run, but did not yield a qualitative improvement in output coherence.

A final pretraining run was conducted using 100% of the training corpus, with an initial learning rate of 2×10^{-4} and a 3% warm-up ratio. This run crashed for an unknown reason during the third epoch and was resumed from the checkpoint saved at the end of the second epoch; the full run took approximately 4 days, 4 hours and 39 minutes. The qualitative characteristics of the resulting base model's output were similar to those of the earlier runs: text remained thematically coherent at the entity level but exhibited persistent grammatical errors and a lack of overall factual or narrative coherence. These weights were nevertheless used as the basis for the subsequent fine-tuning phase, as they represented the best-performing pretrained checkpoint obtained.

3.2 Fine-tuning

An initial fine-tuning run was conducted on a 25% subset of the training data for two epochs, using a reduced learning rate of 5×10^{-5} motivated by prior evidence that lower learning rates may improve fine-tuning outcomes [44], a batch size of 32 and a 3% warm-up ratio; this run took approximately 19 hours and 50 minutes. Qualitative inspection of titles generated for a sample evaluation article showed that the model had learned to produce short, topic-relevant titles consistent in style with the training data, but four of five sampled outputs for a single article contained factual hallucinations and outputs were stylistically repetitive.

The final fine-tuning run used 100% of the training data over three epochs and took approximately 4 days and 23 hours. The loss curve followed a similar trajectory to the 25% run, with a plateau during the third epoch suggesting limited additional gains from further training. Titles generated using the final weights for the same sample article were more consistent in quality and contained fewer apparent factual errors than those from the 25%-data run, although they remained stylistically homogeneous. This final fine-tuned model was used for the formal evaluation reported below.

3.3 Automated evaluation: ROUGE-L and BERTScore

On the 1,000-sample evaluation set, greedy decoding with the SLM produced 14 titles identical in wording to the corresponding original titles and nine empty outputs. GPT-4o produced a single duplicate title relative to the originals and no empty outputs.

As shown in Figure 1, the median ROUGE-L score for SLM titles compared with original titles was approximately 0.40 (mean 0.432), compared with a median of approximately 0.26 (mean 0.286) for GPT-4o titles compared with original titles. SLM scores showed a wider spread (interquartile range 0.25–0.60) than GPT-4o scores (interquartile range 0.174–0.385), which were more tightly clustered around their lower median. The SLM-vs-GPT-4o comparison yielded an intermediate median of approximately 0.286 (mean 0.312).

For the SLM-vs-original comparison (Figure 2), three of the five BERTScore models yielded a median F1 of approximately 0.80; the German BERT base model (gbert-base) yielded a lower median of approximately 0.67, and the multilingual model (multilingual-e5-base) yielded a notably higher median of approximately 0.91. Outliers at zero correspond to the nine empty SLM outputs, and exact duplicates received a BERTScore of 1.0.

For the GPT-4o-vs-original comparison, medians across the five embedding models ranged from approximately 0.61 to 0.88, with most German-language models yielding medians in the range 0.70–0.79 – in each case lower than the corresponding SLM-vs-original medians, accompanied by an increased number of high-value outliers, consistent with a subset of GPT-4o titles showing very high semantic alignment with the original despite lower overall central tendency.

Figure 1: Distribution of ROUGE-L (F1) scores for the three pairwise comparisons: SLM vs. original titles, GPT-4o vs. original titles, and SLM vs. GPT-4o titles.

Figure 2: Distribution of BERTScore (F1) values per embedding model for the comparison of SLM-generated titles (candidates) against original titles (references).

For the SLM-vs-GPT-4o comparison, medians ranged from approximately 0.62 to 0.89 across models, indicating moderate-to-high semantic overlap between the two systems' outputs despite differences in surface form. Overall, the automated metrics indicate that SLM-generated titles were, on average, more closely aligned with the original reference titles than GPT-4o-generated titles.

3.4 Human evaluation

Across the five participants and 100 articles (500 rankings per title type), GPT-4o-generated titles were ranked first most frequently (231 times), followed by the original titles (157 times) and the SLM-generated titles (112 times) (Figure 3). For second-place rankings, the SLM received 159 votes, close to the 192 votes received by the original titles and slightly higher than the 149 votes received by GPT-4o. For third-place rankings, the SLM received 229 votes, substantially more than either the original titles (151) or GPT-4o (120).

Figure 3: Distribution of first-, second-, and third-place rankings assigned by five human evaluators across 100 articles, by title origin (original, SLM, GPT-4o).

In order to verify if there exists a significant difference in the rankings between the three titles, the Friedman Test was applied. The test returns a p-value of $\sim 4.88 * 10^{-12}$. This is far below the thresholds of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis can be rejected. The differences regarding the preference between the original titles and those generated by the SLM or GPT-4o are not due to chance. This supports the previous observations that the titles differ systematically. Furthermore, the Wilcoxon test was applied to check if each possible combination differs systematically as well.

The Post-hoc Wilcoxon tests showed significant differences between all pairs. Both comparison involving the original titles have highly significant differences. However, the difference between the ranking scores of the SLM and GPT-4o is relatively large. This suggests that these two titles are perceived very differently by the participants.

Comparison	<i>p</i> -value
Original vs. SLM	0.000101
Original vs. GPT-4o	0.001253
SLM vs. GPT-4o	$\approx 3.0 \times 10^{-12}$

Table 1: Pairwise Wilcoxon signed-rank test results for the human evaluation rankings.

Taken together, the human evaluation indicates that GPT-4o-generated titles were preferred most often by domain-expert evaluators, that the original titles were preferred over SLM-generated titles and that the SLM-generated titles were most frequently ranked last.

3.5 Inference time

Table 3.5 summarizes the measured inference times for the SLM and GPT-4o across the 1,000 evaluation samples. The SLM showed a substantially lower median inference time (0.160 s) than GPT-4o (0.617 s) and a markedly narrower distribution (Figure 4). One GPT-4o measurement of approximately 10.5 s was excluded from the plotted distribution as a distorting outlier.

It should be noted that this comparison is not fully controlled. The SLM was run locally without any network overhead whereas GPT-4o latency includes network transmission and external API processing time within the production application.

Figure 4: The visualized distributions of the inference time for the SLM and GPT-4o. One outlier of GPT-4o ($\sim 10.512s$) has been removed to prevent its distorting effect and improve the readability of the plot.

Model	n	Mean	Median	SD	Min	25%	75%	Max
SLM	1,000	0.174	0.160	0.065	0.012	0.135	0.205	1.176
GPT-4o	1,000	0.733	0.617	0.471	0.402	0.548	0.738	10.512

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of inference time (in seconds) for the SLM and GPT-4o across 1,000 evaluation samples.

4 Discussion

4.1 Main findings

The prototype is capable of generating useful titles in most cases. It has $\sim 113.6M$ parameters which is significantly less than the working definition of $1B$ parameters. The model has been trained solely on the data provided by APA and has not learned any unlicensed material. The measurements also indicate that its inference time is shorter or on a similar level compared to GPT-4o.

However, with respect to the main research question, the quality of the titles generated by the SLM is not systematically better or at least indistinguishable from the original titles or those generated by GPT-4o. The results for ROUGE-L and BERTSCORE indicate that the SLM titles are more closely aligned with the original titles. Furthermore, both the original titles and those by GPT-4o are significantly preferred more often by human annotators.

4.2 Comparison with previous work

The overall strategy pretraining and fine-tuning a domain- and task-specific model reflects a common approach for developing resource-efficient models [45]. While prior work has reported cases in which small or fine-tuned models outperform substantially larger LLMs on specific tasks [6, 7, 8], this pattern was not observed in the human evaluation conducted here.

Prior work on title generation based on the abstracts of research-papers has shown that fine-tuned models in a similar parameter range from 139M to 568M parameters, including PEGASUS-large, T5-base, and BART-base, achieved ROUGE-L and BERTScore values comparable to or exceeding those of substantially larger LLMs such as GPT-3.5 and LLaMA-3-8B [25]. Furthermore the results of the smaller models were also preferred in a human evaluation [25]. A plausible explanation for the discrepancy between these results and the present findings is that PEGASUS-large was itself pretrained on a summarization-oriented objective [46].

Separately, a study evaluating small models for news summarization under zero-shot conditions has found that such models underperform larger models in terms of BERTScore, coherence, and detail retention [28], suggesting that task-specific fine-tuning is an important factor for SLM performance. Knowledge distillation has also been shown to allow small student models to match or exceed the performance of larger teacher models on summarization tasks while improving inference efficiency [47]; although KD was deliberately not used in this study for licensing reasons, it remains a candidate strategy for future iterations.

4.3 Implications

The potential impact of the SLM must be considered within the context of APA. The model could prevent costs which are caused by the usage of external models like GPT-4o. This includes manual usage by editors as a tool for content creation. Since the model can be deployed on a commercial laptop, the costs for deployment would be relatively low. Theoretically, this would allow a higher number of requests. This would benefit any process where large amounts of texts require titles. An example application could be the automated generation of titles for social media posts and comments. Furthermore, using a local model makes the company less vulnerable to price changes or restrictions imposed by model providers. The SLM could also strengthen the trust of the user in the respective applications and prevent some concerns regarding data privacy and the usage of unlicensed material during development. However, before the SLM can be deployed, its limitations should be addressed.

4.4 Limitations

Although the titles of the SLM are more aligned with the style of the originals on average, they are less likely to be preferred by participants than the originals or GPT-4o. A possible explanation for this discrepancy is that the dominant style of titles in the training data is less likely to be preferred by the annotators than the longer titles of GPT-4o. The participants are media employees with domain knowledge but not journalists who might have ranked the titles differently. This could explain why the LLM has won more often than the originals. Furthermore, the SLM does generate titles that are incomplete and do not have a correct sentence structure. An example of an insufficient generation can be found in the test examples for the human evaluation:

'Ukraine Selenskyj-Bürochef'

The ROUGE-L and BERTScore may fail to capture such mistakes. The human evaluation, on the other hand, can take into account any structural or content-related mistakes by giving those titles a lower rank. However, the rankings test does not show if a specific suggestion has a mistake and if it can be classified as an adequate title. Therefore, additional forms of evaluation are required, for example using an LLM as a judge. Furthermore, the base model is not yet able to complete sequences that are grammatically and factually correct. Although the goal was to generate coherent text, the pretrained model did not yet achieve this. This is an obstacle for any task-specific versions of the SLM that should generate longer texts such as summarizations. The poor quality of the base model points to potential problems with training data, the model configuration or the parameters of the pretraining. Any complication with one of these aspects might have negatively influenced downstream performance as well. Thus, both the pretraining and the fine-tuning should be improved.

4.5 Further research

For example, the composition of the training data could be changed. Currently, it is made up only of news articles from APA. More diverse datasets could expand the knowledge and capabilities of an LLM and can improve the performance for different tasks [48]. Therefore, additional data sources should be acquired and preprocessed while avoiding any unlicensed material. A study also suggests training a model on multiple domains at first, before performing a second pretraining with domain-specific data to improve performance [49].

In addition, the configuration of the SLM requires further attention. Smaller and larger variants of the model need to be created in order to identify any positive trends. The impact of the parameters, especially those that have not been modified through the custom configuration, must be further studied. Furthermore, different model configurations in addition to Gemma3CausalLM should be examined under the same conditions to identify potential alternatives.

The training approach also leaves room for improvement, for example the implementation of LoRa. This method adds trainable low-rank matrices while keeping the original model weights frozen, making adaptation much more efficient and potentially improving results [50]. Furthermore, reinforcement learning with a reward score has been applied for a summarization task [51]. In general, these aspects must be considered for any further development of the SLM.

4.6 Conclusion

The results have shown that a domain-specific SLM is a feasible alternative to an external general-purpose LLMs. Further improvements could lead to sufficient results and provide a solution to many problems associated with large general-purpose models.

Author Contributions

Lorenz Duelli conducted the research as part of the master's thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master's thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien. Christoph Redl supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

Conflicts of Interest

This research was conducted in cooperation with the Austria Presse Agentur and the APA-IT Informations Technologie GmbH, which provided the training and evaluation data, computational infrastructure, access to GPT-4o, and human evaluation participants. Lorenz Duelli is a junior software developer at APA-Tech and Andreas Mauczka is the CDO of APA.

Data Availability

The training and evaluation datasets used in this study consist of material from the APA news archive and cannot be made publicly available, as they constitute the intellectual property of APA. The same principle applies to the model weights.

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Complete configuration of the SLM

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